

A CRITICAL ANALYSIS OF STAKEHOLDERS INTERRELATION AND STUDENTS DISCIPLINE IN KENYAN SCHOOLS

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Abstract:

The purpose of the study was a critical analysis on stakeholders' interrelation and students discipline in Kenyan schools. For discipline to be upheld different stakeholders have to come together and forge a healthy interrelation. That is the; Government, Board of management, parents, teachers and students stakeholders contribute to discipline of any learning institution. Every stakeholder has a role to play as the findings bring out. Every stakeholder participates in policy making and healthy interrelation aids smooth running of schools. Without good interrelation between stakeholders the findings show that school unrest rise and student disagree by protesting. Good interrelation is seen to improve learning environment which leads to improved discipline. The findings established that not only is unhealthy interrelation between students and other stakeholders but also between parents, Board of management, Government and teachers. Indiscipline on any part of stakeholder has resulted to conflict and unhealthy interrelation. The purpose of the study critically analyzes the stakeholders' interrelation and students discipline in Kenyan schools. The study aims at analyzing the Board of Management, Parents, Teachers, Students and The Ministry of Education interrelation and students discipline in Kenyan schools. The study recommends a comprehensive policy by all stakeholders and guidelines that would inform and improve the need to interrelate among the stakeholders. In conclusion the role of all stakeholders in maintaining the students discipline in Kenyan schools wholly depends on interrelation between the stakeholders.

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1. Introduction

Stakeholder's relationship has been a concern in Kenyan society, pertaining the discipline of student in school. For discipline to be upheld, stakeholders are involved hence their relationship in dialogue and decision making important. In recent time, schools have experienced strikes and burning of school property which has highly been blamed on poor stakeholders' dialogue and relationship. Parents, teachers, community, Board of management, Administrators and students are in constant disagreement on how best to manage student discipline.

The National Education Association (NEA) is an organization that is educating Kenyan schools how to improve the quality of achievement through stakeholders' relationship. It released a publication policy "parent family community involvement in education" (2008). It elaborated on how the whole community plays its role in developing the young person in Kenyan School. How stakeholders relate will determine the discipline of students, teachers and community. When one of the stakeholders is left out, the discipline seems to fail as well.

2. Statement of Problem

Over time stakeholders have been entirely engaged in running of schools in Kenya. The government expects discipline of learners in all secondary schools to be managed by the stakeholders. It poses a challenge for any discipline to be upheld for it totally depends on stakeholders' interrelation and how they dialogue from time to time. In recent time 2016, conflicts have escalated leading to torching of schools by learners. The ministry of education released the causes of indiscipline in Kenyan schools as bad blood between the administrators, head teachers, deputy head teachers, teachers and parents, poor communication and some of stakeholders being clueless on what and how to engage others. For stakeholders to run schools effectively, dialogue and good interrelationship is needed. The blame has it that some of stakeholders have incited others leading to high indiscipline cases and school unrest. Constant meeting to enhance working relationship is vital in maintaining student's discipline.

3. Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study was to critically analyze the stakeholder's interrelation and student's discipline, the benefits and ways of improving discipline through healthy interrelation among stakeholders in Kenyan schools.

4. Research Objectives

1. To critically analyze the board of management interrelation and students discipline in Kenyan schools
2. To critically analyze the student interrelation and students discipline in Kenyan schools.
3. To critically analyze the parents interrelation and students discipline in Kenyan schools.
4. To critically analyze the teachers interrelation and students discipline in Kenyan schools.
5. To critically analyze the ministry of education interrelation and students discipline in Kenyan schools.

5. Research Questions

1. To what extent are Board of Management interrelation and students discipline in Kenyan schools?
2. What is the student's interrelation and school discipline in Kenyan schools?
3. What is the parent's interrelation and students discipline in Kenyan schools?
4. To what extent are teacher's interrelation and students discipline in Kenyan schools?
5. What is the ministry of education and students discipline in Kenyan schools?

6. Significance of the Study

The study may help in understanding the stakeholder's interrelation and dialogue in upholding discipline of students in schools. The stakeholders and their role in discipline through dialogue and healthy interrelation with other stakeholders; Teachers, parents, Boards of management parent's, Ministry of education and students is emphasized as the key requirement in upholding discipline in Kenyan schools.

The study may enlighten the stakeholders on importance of interrelationship in maintaining discipline. Constant dialogue may guide the way the school run and avoid tendencies of students' indiscipline. The administrators and teachers find themselves termed not listening and also failing in proper communication. Most of indiscipline cases such as burning of schools have been viewed as a protest by students against leadership of any affected school. It is a way of putting forward their grievances due to failed interrelation between stakeholders their students may benefit in that the enhanced interrelation will bring about dialogue by all stakeholders including students. This may create a better forum to discuss student's needs. Relationship enhances discipline among the stakeholders and curbing indiscipline. Stakeholder's interrelationship also encourages better working condition and dialogue in times of misunderstanding.

7. Theoretic Framework

The study is based on collegial model by Bush (2003) Bush describes management by participation as transformational in leadership especially school policies which are achieved through stakeholders involvement. Freeman of McCrea 2001 emphasizes how crucial it is to focus on the interrelationships in an institution with its stakeholders, try to strike a balance by engaging the stakeholders' relation and the objectives set. The institutions should understand influences by others in order to achieve its objectives, Freeman & McCrea 2001. Donaldson Preston 1995, came up with instrumental approaches which explain ways institutions achieve its objectives by engaging various stakeholders with their principles and practice to achieve its traditional objective.

8. Research Methodology

The study is a critical analysis on stakeholders' interrelation and students discipline in Kenyan schools .The study are done through qualitative method which brings out creativity and factual reliable information. Through this method, the researchers bring out importance of stakeholders interrelation and students discipline in Kenyan schools. William Glassier 1997 in his reality and choice theories, states that individuals involved in decision making on behavior tend to own it and support it. The methodology evaluates different stakeholders' involvement and their interrelation and students discipline in Kenyan schools and also the advantages and disadvantages of poor interrelation among stakeholders.

9. Literature Review Critique

9.1 A Critical Analysis of Board of Management Interrelationship with Stakeholders and School Discipline

The board of management in a school plays a role of ensuring they develop healthy interrelationship with key stakeholders. It also develops effective communication challenges between the involved stakeholders especially in maintaining discipline. In recent time in Kenyan, Schools 2016, burning of schools and endless strikes had highly been blamed on Board of Management breakdown of communication between stakeholders. The Board of management has a role of anticipating problems as much as possible and act to diffuse it. In this case the burning of schools.

Harrison, 1996, on instrumental perspective on stakeholder theory, justifies the stakeholders especially on management that enhances the ability to predict and control the external environment. The concept of Board of management relationship with other stakeholders will enable the schools maintain discipline and also predict possible focus from the environment and also put forth best practices of enhancing dialogue. It is through proper communication channels established by the Board of management that will improve discipline.

9.2 Parent's Interrelation as Stakeholders and Students Discipline in Kenyan Schools

Students come from the society and from different homes where every family stands for certain values. Parents are vital component as interested parties in their children discipline. Parents need to understand and follow keenly what their children are learning in school. Anderson, 1998; Cooperman, 1999; Quezada, 2003, emphasize on collaborative involvement in school practices and parental involvement because it moves the school closer to the community parents.

Due to high tension and a very unfriendly environment blamed by most school going students the parents participation uplifts students motivation, boost their morale and also improve how they engage and commit according to Beverley, Freedman McGee, Moran, 2003. When parent's commitment is in good relationship, discipline is likely achieved. Highly motivated parents will support the stakeholder's interrelationship and engage to improve students discipline in Kenyan schools. Parents are expected by the government policy to support the implementation of school discipline policy. Healthy interrelationship helps in easy implementation of discipline policies (May 2006) Government policy.

9.3 Student's Interrelationship as Stakeholders and School Discipline

In any learning institution the interrelationship between stakeholders affect students directly and the discipline among students highly depends on the dialogue and effective communication. When the students fail to be involved in policy making by the government, formulation of school roles, expectations from the society and lack of involvement of students could lead to unrests as experienced in most schools in Kenya. The goals, policies, objectives and decisions arrived by stakeholders affect the learners positively if the interrelationship through proper communication is achieved.

Representation and participation aids the learners own up their decision arrived at and also take part in their formulation. Ann Svendsen 2010 emphasizes the bridging techniques where she sees stakeholders as being reciprocal. An institution will be better in dealing with changes in environment early when they have a good relationship between them.

According to Kenyan Government policy, all students are expected to follow the set discipline code and also follow what is set by the administrators, teachers, parents, board of management and society deemed appropriate as accepted behaviour. This has brought problems as students view it dictatorial. Good dialogue and discipline solves this problem by enhancing co-operation and relationship. Government policy (May 2006)

9.4 Teachers Interrelation as Stakeholders and School Discipline

Discipline is a learning process which develops students on how to develop self-discipline .It develops students thinking and moral faculties. Learning process involves the teacher in guiding and building the students competencies. Discipline requires good interrelationship through healthy collaboration between stakeholders. Teachers are the direct players who engage students in daily activities.

Healthy dialogue and teachers participation in formulating rules and implementing the objectives is highly unavoidable. Lack of co-operation and participation by teachers is felt directly by the institution as they play a passive position where as are expected to engage the learners by guiding their behavior. According to Government policy (May 2006) teachers are expected to participate in developing discipline policy and support its effective implementation.

9.5 The Government Interrelation as Stakeholders and School Discipline

Policies, national education goals, objectives are formulated by the government on ways to achieve on both academic and discipline of students. Most of schools in Kenya are directly financed by the government. All other stakeholders are held together for a

common goal. The interrelationship among the government and the school stakeholders will ensure discipline of all stakeholders.

Power fights trickles down to students'. Any unhealthy interrelationship between stakeholders affects the discipline of the school. Government policy states that good discipline is fundamental and schools must have a discipline policy developed in consultation which leads to healthy interrelationship. Government policy (May 2006).

9.6 Stakeholders Interrelation and Students' Discipline

William Glassier 1997 His reality and choice theories state that when individuals are involved in decision making on their behavior they tend to own it. Their self-esteem and pride in their participation help in maintaining discipline. Gordon Thomas 1974 on teacher effectiveness training explains that good interrelationship between stakeholders charged in maintaining discipline and the student is more important than what is taught. The good interrelationship and communication help in conflict resolution and maintaining of students disciplined.

Rundolf Dreikurs 1972 emphasized that discipline is based on respect which motivates and improve relationship between stakeholders John Dewey 1916 believed in democratic a practice which is based on good interrelationship. Interrelationship is the fast step in achieving discipline among stakeholders.

10. Conclusion

The findings suggest that good interrelation among stakeholder is the key to improvement of discipline in Kenyan schools. Dialogue and participation of all stakeholders; Board of management, Government, teachers, parents and students is essential for it improves interrelation among stakeholders hence improving students discipline and avoiding problems like school unrests in Kenyan schools. Most of school indiscipline tendencies are as a result of unhealthy communication among the involved stakeholders.

Every stakeholder has a role to play pertaining discipline in a school. No single stakeholder without collaboration can deal with school discipline. Participation and good relation ensures communication to minimize conflict

11. Recommendations

1. All the Board of Management stakeholders need to cultivate healthy interrelation to maintain students' discipline. Their unhealthy interrelation also goes down to

the student's discipline. The Board of Management has a role of involving all stakeholders in improving stakeholders' interrelation.

2. Every student is directly affected by any policy and objectives set for a school. Students have a role to play on their discipline. Healthy interrelation enhances good understanding and solution based approach.
3. The parent's stakeholders' participation in formulation of rules, objectives and goals is essential. Good, interrelation will improve discipline and smooth running of schools as all students belong to a society where parents come from.
4. Representation should be encouraged for all stakeholders to feel part of the institution and freedom to participate with healthy interrelation that no one is left out. Comprehensive policies on interrelation between teachers need to be spelt out. Teachers are policy and implementers of the set policies. Their participation should be put into consideration to improve on students' discipline.
5. For there to be a smooth running of schools the Ministry of Education need to participate and inclusion of all in policy, objectives and goals setting. Healthy relation needs to be emphasized at all schools levels pertaining students discipline.

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